

MARGINALIZATION AND SUBJECTIVITY: AN ECO-CRITICAL STUDY OF QURATUL AIN HAIDER'S FIREFLIES IN THE MIST

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Abstract

The research deals with the topic of marginalization and subjectivity from the perspective of ecocriticism in Haider's novel *Fireflies in the Mist* which is written in the context of postcolonialism, showing the not only distorted position of the locality but the oppression and exploitation of both male and female. The larger portion of the story revolves around the female objectivity that is enabled through the ecocritical disposition, helping the female characters, particularly the protagonist of the story to handle the situation and get out of marginalized proxies and becoming an agentic entity. Thus, the agentic characters become the subjective entities. Therefore, the current research deals with the intended phenomenon of marginalization and subjectivity which has been researched in Haider's selected novel from the perspective of both postcolonialism and ecocriticism, showing how the protagonist of the novel revolves around different spectacles of both oppression, marginalization and subjectivity, becoming a popular character. This trajectory has been made successful by the environmental shelters in the novel which is the major finding of the research.

INTRODUCTION

This study aims to focus on the relationship between human and non-human present in the novel *Fireflies in the Mist* (1994) composed by Quratul Ain Haider in the perspective of Postcolonialism. Ecocriticism is a young movement in literary criticism that finds relationship between man and his surroundings, and how marginalized people lead themselves to the context of subjectivity through eco-critical world. The research further focuses on the nexus between human and the physical settings which is non-human including environment, animals and all the commodities of nature. Ecocriticism is defined as

“The study of the relationship of the human and the non-human, throughout human cultural history and entailing critical analysis of the term ‘human’itself” (Garrard, 2011, P. 5). In response to the environmental crises, the Ecocritics propagated through literary criticism to bring consciousness regarding the importance of environment in human life. The impact of surroundings and environment can not be ignored in the lives of human being because both influence each other. The issues regarding environment are due to the mishandling of man and in return the environment also disturbs the

lives of human beings. So the relationship between man and the natural world is inevitable.

The researcher has based the study on the idea that the natural entities, the physical scenario, the environmental commodities all contribute to influence and shape the lives of the human beings especially in the case of a colonized place. The lands colonized by the clonial powers were target for them to deteriorate not only the culture but also the environment. The colonizers not only exploited human beings of the colonized but also non-human. Because to control on the land during the colonized tenure was not easy only to control the people but also the whole milieu in which the colonized existed. The colonial powers penetrated their imperial paws in those lands which were rich in natural resources with economic benefits for them. But the subjugated people were treated as inferior and savages who were made to realize that the colonial powers wanted to civilize them. Their intentions were terrible that not only ventured the people but also their abode land and ultimately the whole mileu which aroused countless issues regarding colonialism, like diaspora, hybridity, identity and marginalization.

Background and reviews on Ecocriticism

Love (2003) describes the emerging relation between non-human and man that is termed as *Ecocriticism* in which human and non-human considerations are brought at the same forum. He describes various ecocritics in the book with different kind of perspectives towards ecology. He states that presence of nature in literature finds its place from so many years. He associates the works of British and American writers with the natural environment. Glen's biological incorporation with the Darwanian concept marks the ecocritical concepts for the basis of the environmental ecocriticism and biological variation in human nature. A great bulk on literature revolves around the pastoral -orientation but not with specification on a separate theory as now it owns the title of *Ecocriticism*. He focuses the attention of ecocritics to analyse and meditate on literature with new dimensions of nature. Love stresses how *Darwinian ideas* are influential for Ecocritical perspectives and biological dimension. He emphasizes that change in human beings is directly related to nature.

Buell (1995) states about literary collision with culture and their impacts on nature. Nature's repercussion on literary text echoes Buell's approach in a traditional way to encapsulate literature and history in the same thread. Buell feels the need to search new ways to have congruity between literature and environment. His main consideration is to represent nature in the literary text, where Thoreau's *Walden* is milestone representing the natural background. Buell describes the literary history of environmental perception. Non-human environment is not considered as marginalizing as a frame, surrounding the literary text but to identify that the the human histroy is coiled within the lace of natural history. He defines the importance of environment as an ethical orientation within the text. Buell exhibits a thorough pattern of pastoral environment in American literature and it is considered the most identifiable work related to Ecocriticism. He suggests the criteria for ecocritical work which should be truly the ecocritical oriented literary work.

Garrard (2012) provides detailed information about ecocriticism. According to him Ecocriticism traces the ways to explore the relationship between the human and the natural environment in all respects. He investigates the ways to imagine and find the compatibility between the human and non-human world. According to Garrard the relationship between environment and culture varies with the passage of time because the difference in cultures modifies the term in different sense but both the Culture and Ecocriticism occupy a significant integrity without amalgamating with each other.

Carson (1962) presents the relationship between man and his surroundings. He believes that the patrol sense of relief is deteriorated through the pesticides for birds. Carson laments for the birds and animals that are badly affected by the harmful environment showing the importance of environment for living organisms. He comes up with the opinion that human being are also suffering from dangerous diseases like cancer because of bad influence of the environment. He highlights the beauty of nature and its compatibility with the human being. Carson describes the deterioration firstly caused by supernatural power by describing the poem of keats where the grass is withered not by the magical powersbutbythe human beings. Carson mentions countless bird's chirping

and animals' grazing focusing on the surrounding which paves the ways for environmentalism in literature. He describes the involvement of nature in which the life of rural area in America is quite peaceful with its natural physical world.

William (1975) states the best combination of life between countryside and city. He traces the images of country in contrast with city in English literature. His association with his birth place in country is attached with the ecology of the place. According to him the pastoral milieu leads back towards past which is full of mirth. He describes his association with the countryside and the natural environment in which the songs of mirth show compatibility with the external world.

Howarth (1996) associates all the objects of nature in a strong bond of relation with culture. He negates the basic concern of the writers who focus only on language and even the critics who think that language is the only essence in literary study. While the ecocritics according to Howarth focus on the relation between nature and the present culture in a strong bond that gets mixed with each other as water gets amalgamated with soil in the stream (P. 69). For Howarth four specific principles support for the work of Ecocriticism that are ecology ethics, language, and criticism (p. 71). These disciplines provide a proper way and method to point out environmental and natural literature. In this essay Howarth explains about ecology which is conspicuous to narrate the history and past of the land. Through this discipline the interpretation regarding the history of land is possible. He believes that ecology is a central shift which leads literature from human views to environment. Ethics stands in close relation with ecology which becomes a central point in environmental literature with reference to criticism.

Coupe (2000) writes about the environment by collecting material related to ecology from the era of Romanticism to the modern literature. Coupe believes that the surrounding environment like forests, rivers and other objects of nature which are included in greenery are our fellow-beings and must be treated in good terms. He states that instead of Ecocriticism the term Green Studies clicks such kind of works. Bate (2000) states about destruction of the earth. He finds out the relationship between culture, environment and consciousness regarding nature

which focuses that human relation with nature has been ignored. Bate focuses the attention of human to maintain relation with nature because deforestation and imperialism have deformed the face of land through their adverse effects on it.

Slovic (2010) mentions that third wave regarding Ecocriticism explores all kind of human aspects of relationship with nature. According to him the association between human experience and the prevailing environment has great association with culture.

Oppermann (1999) believes that interpretation of a text on the basis of nature and the interaction of the ecological ideology ultimately lead towards the issues of environment which investigates the text in the perspective of not only on natural consciousness but also of ecological sciences. He believes that this kind of interpretation opens the ways for discourse on global environmental issues which identifies the literary work to an ecocritical-oriented criticism (P. 31)

Kerridge (1998) finds relationship between literary text and ideology of Ecocriticism which contribute to highlight the issues related to environment. He states that the Ecocritics want to find out environmental perspectives with cultural crises.

Garrard (2011) states that the orientation of ecocritical work is specified through nature writing including the romantic poetry and narration of environmental wilderness in literature. But after the organization of ASLE states Garrard Ecocriticism diverted towards the distinct and translucent turns of studies through TV scientific writing and art. He describes the various notable dimensions of different cultures related to Ecocriticism specially with reference to British and American literature with the historical background of the cultures within which the literary writings revolve.

Garrard states that culture is considered to be confined within the framework of nature which is a limited ideology regarding Ecocriticism but the fact is that both go parallel in their implementation. According to Garrard the Ecocritics unveil the complicated labyrinths of compatibility between culture and nature through different cultural antiquity with multiple themes and concepts like zoo, fields, greenery, parks and other resorts. Garrard highlights Ecocriticism through various medium of

production. He says that culture and nature depend upon each other as the environmental crises arise due to crises in culture because the association between the ecological non-human world and the culture is the outcome of the direct interaction of culture and nature.

Howrath (1996) states that the relationship between ecology and ethics remained the specific concern to relate ecology with ethical and social issues. He further says that through ecology the history of the land relating to environment is preserved in literature and explains about language which is another integral discipline to explore the importance of words arrangement that exhibits the association between the human and non-human entities. According to him Ecocriticism can not be acknowledged without its compatibility with the cultural, environmental legacy and natural sciences because they are of great concern for language which focus on the culture of human ideology as the expression of language in science which provides the foundation to describe the land and its environment.

Dr. Tripathi (2016) in her article analyses the Ecocritical elements in the novel of Hardy's *Return Of The Native* where nature plays its part as a *Character*. The landscape in the novel presents the acute picture of Ecocriticism which is embodied within the framework of nature. According to her *Return of the Native* presents the authentic picture of Ecocriticism where the relationship between man and nature depicts the writer's bent to characterize nature as a significant character that influences the lives of all the characters. The *Return of the Natives* (1978) by Hardy shows a strong compatibility between man and nature. Egdon Heath plays a vital role as a character in the lives of all the important characters of the novel. Holloway (1962) observes that Hardy's characters are "governed by and subdued to their environment" (p.266). It's the environment of the Heath which does not allow any character of the novel to act against its nature.

The story of the novel can be understood by the surrounding and the physical settings of the novel which is Heath that gives the novel the Ecocritical dimension. All the characters are defined under the influence of Heath. The person who goes against the nature of Heath, it becomes crucial for him.

The protagonist, Eustacia does not like Heath. She dislikes living at Heath. She wants to go to Paris to enjoy her life there. That's why she marries Clym who lives in Paris. Nature is mysterious in this novel. It does not allow any character to go against it. As in the case of Eustacia it becomes cruel when she wants to leave it. The storm causes the death of Eustacia as she is unable to see the light of moon and stars. Nature becomes horrible for her. She gets scared to see her surrounding mysterious, she begins to tremble "over twisted furze-roots, tufts of rushes, or oozing lumps of fleshy fungi, which at this season lay scattered about the heath like the rotten liver and lungs of some colossal animal" (Hardy, 1978, p. 420). Clym who does not come up to the level of Eustacia and comes back to Egdon Heath and gives preference to there in the lap of nature, starts to live there as furze cutter. He likes Heath, while Eustacia dislikes it. That's why Heath is friendly to Clym but an enemy for Eustacia. For Wildeve, who plans with Eustacia to leave Heath, it becomes hostile to both. But for Clym and Diggory who wants to live in Heath happily, it becomes a hope for them. Walter Allen (1954) says, "Hardy's intent to show that the stars in their courses fight against the aspiring, the man or woman who would rise above the common lot through greatness of spirit, of ambition, or passion" (p.251). Clym wants to remain in the lap of natural atmosphere. That's why he rejects the glimmering and artificial life of Paris. But Eustacia does not like this and she decides to leave him. The ecology of Heath does not allow anyone to act against its environment. So it is unfavourable for Eustacia. Ernest Baker (1938) says "The chief character ... is embodied this time in Egdon Heath, the dark, immemorial environment whose influences control obscurely the lives and destinies of those who dwell contentedly amid its gorsy wilderness or feel themselves cruelly out of their element. Egdon Heath symbolizes the whole cosmic order, in which man is but an insignificant particle." (p.36)

Tripathi (2016) states that Ecocriticism awakes the modern man's consciousness towards the environmental influence on human beings and their perception to perceive the ecological consciousness regarding nature and environment. He comes up with the opinion that right from 1990s texts are interpreted through the canon of Ecocriticism as signified and a separate theoretical ground in literature.

Ganguly (2017) explores in his article *An Ecocritical Approach to Anita Desai's Fire on the Mountain* the ecocritical elements in the novel. He says that Ecocriticism is a newly emerging theory which traces the deep intimacy between human and the surrounding in which he interacts with nature but he laments for the attitude of man towards nature that is quite indifferent. He believes that man's such kind of ignorant behavior with nature ultimately leads natural environment towards destruction of nature and its unrecoverable effects. He further refers nature as *Mother* that puts its acute impact on human life and drives it towards optimism (P. 240). Nanda is sick of her past life that's why she prefers to live alone in the wild forest "here hills melted into sky, sky into snows, snows into air" (Ainta, 2008. P.30). She observes the wild life very close to human life where everyone is emotionless. She thinks herself like a worm that has become a prey of other animals. Nanda's husband used to ignore her and had love affair with other lady which made her aloof from normal life.

Nanda observes "the white hen drag out a worm inch by resisting inch from the ground till it snapped in two. She felt like the worm herself, she winced at its mutilation" (p.23). Anita brings to surface the emotional feelings of the characters through natural images. Raka, the great granddaughter of Nanda also comes at Carignano, to live with her as she is an ignored child by her parents. Her childhood experiences make her sick from a normal life that a child enjoys in his childhood. That's why she likes the rotten cottage at Kasuli and likes the fire which is burning on the mountain, depicting her inner turmoil.

In Anita's novel the wild ecology of the forest becomes the source of solace for the characters. Nanda and Ila want to escape from the male dominant society. The wild natural atmosphere comforts their souls. The landscape sketched by Anita of Kasauli has close relationship with the nature of the characters. The mountains of Kasauli provide shelter and freedom to Nanda and Raka. These are also a source of fulfillment of their internal feelings. Here nature plays a vital role in redefining the relationship between man and nature.

The natural atmosphere of Kasauli with its alluring landscape, Desai represents the ecology fit for the characters. The mountains full of flora and fauna, fall

of rain, blooming of flowers, gusts, storms, the smell of rotten things represent the changing inner condition of Nanda. The surrounding atmosphere of Carignano with its deserted nature show strong compatibility with the characters. The fire burning on the mountains and the long spells of rain represent the inner rage and turmoil of Raka, who wants to make her tortured soul comfortable in the lap of nature.

Shikha (2011) comes up with the opinion that there exists strong compatibility between culture and the physical milieu and both correspond with each other which exhibits that the culture of man finds its place in the *natural* scenario. According to Shikha the ecocritics investigate the attitude of man towards the environmental crisis in the literary text to judge the interference of nature as a character.

Cheryll Glotfelty published the outstanding and a leading book on Ecocriticism *The Ecocriticism Reader* (1996) describing the root concept on Ecocriticism of different writers with flourishing dimensions towards nature and environment. The coherency between the articles on Ecocriticism and the emerging issues in the essays regarding Literature and its compatibility with Environment by the leading Ecocritics prove her ideas to be a milestone and influential theory in the field of Ecocriticism by Glotfelty and Harold. The ecological approach in the emerging perspectives of Environment in Literature is the soul essence of this book. The literary discourse on ecological aspects by Glotfelty opens new horizons in the realm of literary criticism. Being the pioneer professor in Literature and Environment at the Nevada University, her talent and bent towards nature and environment mark her writings the paragon on Ecocriticism. She states in her book the simplest definition of ecocriticism.

What then is ecocriticism? Simply put, ecocriticism is the study of the relationship between literature and the physical environment. Just as feminism criticism examines language and literature from a gender-conscious perspective, and Marxist criticism brings an awareness of modes of production and economic class to its reading of texts, ecocriticism takes an earth-centered approach to literary studies (Glotfelty, 1996, p. xviii).

William Rueckert and Scott Slovic's concept on *Ecocriticism* will also share the parallel ideas as of Glotfelty. Ecocriticism is not a theory with single idea.

Its implementation and application is as vast as the whole world because it is abound in countless influential strands to investigate many sub-fields related to nature and environment.

Riaz and Hussain (2015) similarly identify postcolonial spaces as pertinent for an eco-critical framework, as their research is situated in Afghanistan. The postcolonial perspective is applicable, and the various literary genres produced are closely aligned with environmental asylum, aiding the marginalised and oppressed in their quest for refuge.

Shah, Riaz, and Khan (2020) examine the eco-critical approach in their research work, investigating several phases of feminism and their reflection of many thematic issues. Shah, Riaz, and Khan (2020) curated poems by female poets addressing many aspects of women's existence. The primary emphasis of the study article by Shah, Riaz, and Khan (2020) is the eco-critical viewpoint on Maya Angelou's "Woman Work." They concentrate on an eco-feminist approach to eradicate the marginalisation and oppression of women, transitioning towards nature. The research also paves the path for a postcolonial analysis of Angelou's work on women to be examined from several perspectives.

Ecocriticism switches to bio-centric approach from the human-centric literary discourse diverting the literary studies into a new direction. Ecocriticism finds the congruity between the human culture and the non-human entities advocating the non-human world a conspicuous part of the human culture. Environment and nature put a paradigm impact on human cultural literary studies highlighting the nature as the most influential part of literature.

Despite the broad scope of inquiry and disparate levels of sophistication, all ecological criticism shares the fundamental premise that human culture is connected to the physical world, affecting it and affected by it. Ecocriticism takes as its subject the interconnections between nature and culture, specifically the cultural artifacts of language and literature (Glotfelty, 1996, p. xix).

Nature as physical environment in literature and art always remained an authentic background but its exposure as a separate literary criticism is mounting higher taking its prominent position in the world of literary studies. The countless texts are interpreted

now on the basis of Ecocriticism. Nature is found in literary texts in various modes of non-human world like; rivers, mountains, plants, culture and animals. The affinity between the surrounding milieu and the man imposing their influence upon each other drives the literary text into the realm of Ecocriticism.

Eden, Arcadia, virgin land, miasmal swamp, wilderness and when absences are noticed: where is the natural world in this text? But nature per se is not the only focus of ecocritical studies of representation. Other topics include the frontier, animals, and cities, specific, geographical regions, rivers, mountains, deserts, Indians, technology, garbage and the body (Glotfelty, 1996, p. xxiii).

Expanding the thoughts of William Rueckert and Scott Slovic, Glotfelty describes the vitality of environment and physical setting as non-human with their peculiar impact on the literary text. William Rueckert first time coined this new emerging term in 1978. In *Literature and Ecology: An Experiment in Literature* (1996). By Ecocriticism Rueckert means "the application of ecology and ecological concepts to the study of literature" (Glotfelty, 1996, p. xx). The link between literature and the surrounding atmosphere of non-human world supports the literary text to be an ecocritical work in its essence.

Ecocriticism analysis the connection of the outer entities as *Physical settings* including, animals, mountains, sky, searh, moon, rivers, plants, geography of the specific place and landscapes with the text categorizing it an Ecocritical oriented work.

Objective stance and subjective whims: An eco-critical Analysis

The land of India with its diversity of different people with different religions embraced Christianity as the English were the ruling class and to acquire the material benefits the Indians did not bother about their basic origins. The conversion of identity apparently brought no harm in their lives but after colonialism it led towards the deterioration of the nation. It was ridiculous for them to be called as Black. "In north India, low-caste converts were often jeeringly referred to as Chamresians-cobblers-to rhyme with Eurasians. They were also called Black Englishmen" (Haider, 1994, p. 75).

The conversion from one religion to another was not an easy process as it seemed in India where people of

different religion and culture were living together for thousands of years. The surrounding environment of the colonized land of Sub-continent began to amalgamate with the western culture to uproot the strong roots of traditions of different culture in the soil of India connected into one country. This all was done through inducting the western culture and religion in this land. The people changed their identity by adopting the western religion and it raised the question on their identity. "At twenty Rosie Shrila Bannerjee was terribly confused" (p. 77).

Rosie, the daughter of Mr. Bannerjee was unable to resolve this dilemma of identity crises where her Brahmin mother still preferred Hindu way of worshipping. For Rosie it became problematic to explain her position, her identity in the society.

This entire system must be changed. A system which allowed such atrocities as perpetrated on her own mother. Now she also wanted to identify with Indian culture and nationalism. Her own "native Christian" society had been created by the British and was generally loyal to its founders. Rosie's saintly father had resolved the dilemma long ago and was happy in his situation. She could not explain her problem to him; he wouldn't understand. Despite her conversion, Esther Giribala was still basically a Bengali Brahmin housewife, uninterested in the problems of identity (Haider, 1994, p. 77).

Rehan a Muslim boy, Deepali a Hindu girl, Mr. Bannerjee a Christian all belonged to the same land representing different religions in the Sub-continent. The people of India once happily united were made separated by the British identifying them differently in their outlook creating conflict between their identity and country. The rising of the sun with its glowing effect on the glorious past of the Indian before colonization speaks louder the prosperity of the land.

The sun burst through the window and lit up the rose pink painting of Lalbagh Fort. It had been built by Emperor Aurangzaib's son, Prince Moohammad Azam, Governor of Bengal, in the seventeenth century. Rehan had said (she had begun to think in the way Rev. Ban. Nerjee would prefix his speech with the phrase: Jesus had said) All our monuments our superlative handicrafts, our music and dance and literature... and all this belong to better times. Our communal tensions and our poverty are the direct

result of British colonialism. The badly exploited agriculture land and a growing population are bound to cause group conflicts (Haider, 1994, p. 160).

The physical settings of the Indian land contributed to a great extent to colonize it by the British. The land full of its natural resources but with the unpolished people was full of fascination for the British. For Rosie her identity was also a question leaving unresolved answers. It was poverty, hunger and misery which forced these people to lose their identity but it led them in the chaos of identity living in their own country. Their own surroundings seemed raising questions about their identity.

Rosie started attending their meetings, and found the answers of too many questions which had been bothering her about her own situation; Britain had turned Indian into a raw-material producing colony. That led to hunger, unemployment and Hindu-Muslim clashes. The situation also gave the White missionaries ample opportunity to convert the starving Indians (Haider, 1994, p. 78).

The land of Sub-continent with its rigidity in culture and tradition was divided on the same basis on which this land felt proud. The identity crises in their own land made them alien to their particular tradition and they became the followers of the British and their religion going against their own land. Rosie makes the binaries of the same religion present in the West and in the East.

But look at Rosie, showed the green flag to Mr. Luther Biswas. I told her, 'both you and I are the products of our particular milieu. How far can you rebel? The Brahmin Christians of Bengal can be very conservative. Your father happens to be one of them, I don't know why Christianity is equated with Western modernity. Basically, it is an orthodox Asian religion (Haider, 1994, p. 129).

The people of India before the arrival of the British had different religion like Hinduism and Islam. But they were living together for thousands of years. The colonial powers brought materialistic benefits that forced them to lose their original identity. But the arrival of the British divided them on the basis of religion and made them aware to be different in every way. But now the identity was the first and foremost issue for all the Indian.

The Zaman Chowdhrys represented a civilization which had been as all-pervasive as the latter-day Age of

victorias. As such, these Bengalis aristocrats of Arjumand Manzil had much in common with the khans of Crimea and Cairo. They were also different from the Khans and Aghas and Pashas of the West, because they were Indians. This inner duality had been no problem in earlier times; now modern concepts of Pan-Islamism and nationalism had turned into a political dilemma (Haider, 1994, pp. 152-153).

Deepali can not comprehend the root dilemma of separate identity after colonization. The British created such haphazardness among the Indian who fell in the enigma of identity and separate nationalism. In their own land they were now different in all respects which in fact led them towards riots. "Nawab Qamrul Zaman Chowdhry is the heir to the Muslim past of Bengal. She recollected that her home district, Mymensingh, contained lovely monuments of Buddhist and Hindu Bengal. So, am I the heir to the Hindu past? Don't these two heritages have any relationship with each other?" (Haider, 1994, p. 160).

Deepali and Rehan are poles apart on the basis of their identity which remains the conspicuous issues to be united for the both lovers. They could be one but the identity issues perches on their fate specially related to the geographically binaries which will separate them. Rehan is optimistic for a new country Pakistan which will emerge as a new country from the land of India because the identity being a Muslim can only be manipulated in a separate land. But it will depart them from each other.

Don't romanticize everything. He may be the Ancient Mariner and that all, what interests me right now is that this may be a staunch follower of the Muslim League, hoping that soon these Indian rivers will turn into Pakistani rivers. Geography is changed by human beings. "The ship master turned around and was greeted by an enthusiastic "Assalam Aleikum" from the young mam. He was now telling his young companion, "Bengal is a Muslim majority province and the Muslim masses are waiting for progressive leadership (Haider, 1994, p. 201).

The Indians were befooled in their own country. The English became the owner of the land at that time even controlling the destiny of the natives. This was all because the natives surrendered themselves in the hand of the British changing their identity. They were

helpless in their own country because switching over from their original identity to another made them alien in their own country. Mr. Barlow was made fun of by the native Indian who lost his original identity being a black and Indian. Like the misty room of Mr. Barlow the Identity of Mr. Bannerjee was also in the mist.

The room looked misty. I am drunk. Hurray! The Black Padre sits in front. I have always wondered how one can change one's ancestral religion. How does one peel off one's skin and wear another? For instance, if I become a Buddhist or a Mohammedan! Ha, ha. The Black Padre dressed in Black suit and white dog collar looks so absurd. Comrade Rehan is absurd. I am absurd. Sir Edward Barlow was absurd. India, the whole world, all humanity is so ludicrous that one ought to weep". Mr. Barlow". "Hmm." Black Padre has come to me with some petition. Must dispense justice, being the Mai-Baap, Father-Mother, of the natives (Haider, 1994, p. 214). The geographically land division of the Sub-continent not only separated the once living together people for thousands years but also created the problems of identity. Their own land became alien for them. The particular identity of a religion made people intruder for each other. Same thing happened with the daughter of Bannerjee who being a Christian married to a Hindu and left her birth place leaving identity issues for her and her parents.

For Rosie's children, I have a feeling they may arrive this evening. There is an airplane service now, between Calcutta and Dacca. "Yes Paul". "We wait for her every Christmas. She doesn't come." Paul it is not very easy for her to travel from India. Visa problems, you know (Haider, 1994, p. 312).

The environment of a Christian house where the celebration for Christmas is being arranged, is mixed with the effects of postcolonial issues of identity. The daughter of Bannerjee changed her identity for the sake of her marriage and brought a distance of boundary of different country which pinches her parents. "She wouldn't be celebrating Christmas now, would she Esther?" he said again." She has become Shrimati Radhika Sanyal. Perhaps even hides former identity. She has totally merged herself with her husband's community" (Haider, 1994, p. 313).

Yasmin Majid a Muslim girl from India for the sake of fame goes to abroad thinking herself to conquer the

world through her talent. This innocent girl is unaware from the the effects of identity crises. She is lost in her success to come abroad as a famous dancer and she weds to an Englishman. She loses her identity and faces endless issues till her death. She is *Black* from the land of Sub-continent and going to marry an English man with other religion.

Dark Dancers Yasmeen Majid with her white Man, the caption read under the photograph. The Barefoot Dancer says, "I am in the seventh heaven of joy, like a houri of paradise!" The picture showed a barefoot Yasmeen in a white sari, being carried in the arms of a grinning Gerald Belmont." *Black Beauty*. Dark Dancer. Is Yasmin a racehorse? Sad. A girl from a family of venerable maulanans of Jalpaiguri-she has come to be called a Barefoot Dancer," Nayyarul Zaman commented ruefully (Haider, 1994, p. 315).

The surrounding of a particular land affects the lives of the people. An alien land never favors the strangers where their identity is challenged. Same thing happened with Yasmin Majid who suffers a lot in other country where she is supposed to be a foreigner and starving in misery. Her daughter has to suffer also Identity crises because of poverty of her mother in other country and she gets rid of her by surrendering her to her grandmother without bothering the loss of her original identity.

Laura Belmont is a stage actress, wealthy and mean. We had a long discussion. She never got along with her only son and does not approve of his lifestyle. She took to her grandchild and offered to bring her up on the condition that she would first be baptized in the Roman Catholic Church. I was so desperate I said. Roman Catholic? You can bring her up as a Seventh-Day dventist, Buddhist, Shinto, Hottentot, whatever, as long as she does not have to starve and knock around like me (Haider, 1994, p. 319).

Yasmeen, a diasporic dancer writes a diary to her friend. The sourrounding of the foreign land does not support her to get stabled there. Separation from her supposed English hasband, her failure as dancer, her undefined identity and alien environment lead her towards frustration.

Now I am clerking in a City office, it was impossible to continue with the troupe, especially after the elopement of my star partner. He had become quite well-known in Europe as an "Oriental" dancer. He is East Pakistani, like me. We could not call ourselves

Indian dancers, although the Maniipuri Khathak, and folk dance of India and Pakistan are the same" (Haider, 1994, p. 319).

The physical environment in the hovering situation of postcolonial perspective corollary the characters. The falling rain also washes away Yasmeen's grieves of being helplessness. She also conceals her identity of being *Black* before her daughter. Her identity crises haunts her till her last breath. Yasmeen tries her best to hide her reality from her daughter and she also wanted her to be away from the glamorous world.

Perhaps she also doesn't want people to know that her mother is colored woman. She is a hazel-eyed brunette and has inherited the stunning good looks of her father. Obviously she does not wish to be known as a mulatto. Today she said bluntly, "Mummy, why do you take the trouble of travelling all the way from London every week to see me? I am all right. This broke my heart. While I stood waiting for the coach, my tears mingled with the rain that lashed my face. Suddenly I felt that someone was watching me (Haider, 1994, p. 331).

Deepali goes with Uma in the temple but her mind is occupied with the pathetic past after colonization when she is in diaspora and has come back in her beloved country visit perhaps for the last time. Her gloomy inner condition and the prevailing doleful scenario of natural atmosphere put their impact on Deepali which enhance her grief about her past, her divided country and her friends. The colonization shatters the vision of the colonized people. Deepali gets dejected while remembering the unexpected circumstances about the lives of Yasmin, Jehan Ara and also of Deepali. In the trance of her beloved country's environment and being in Diaspora she unconsciously reacts.

"O Rower of the painted Boat. You come neither with the ebb. Nor with the flow. Koels sang in the honey months of Chat. Fishermen went out with their nets under the winter moon. Ladybirds buzzed among the summer flowers. "The crazy boat of love sails on the snad as well" Bloody nonsense. One was murdered. One committed suicide. One is and exile" (Haider, 1994 P.389).

Ecology and postcolonialism in their alliance approach work effectively on the lives of the people who are in diaspora, who have been dislocated from

their root land from their environments which results in dispossession.

Same case happens with Yasmin who comes to England to make her dreams come true to be successful dancer. But she remains unconscious of the feeling that the exiled have no their own land. No one accepts them.

When my countrymen meet me here, especially the fellows from Decca, they say with great enthusiasm, come to Karachi. The government will set up a dance academy for you. When I wrote to the ministry at Karachi, there is no response. I am a person of no consequence. Who will pay any attention to me? (Haider, 1994, P.332).

Conclusion

In this novel, Haider's characters move with the waves of sea and river. The tempest and calm of the sea influence the character's life in the form of unrest and peace respectively. All the rivers Padma and Ganga are lagging behind in Deepali's journey of torment at her own homeland. Her journey within the shining sea waves and with the rising morning light ecocritically defines her journey towards exile. Deepali's departure from Bengal shows a sense of relief from the tumult nostalgia towards the endless joys.

She is occupied between the pre-colonialism and post-colonialism chaos, which is now shedding down during her journey within the waves of sea. She is leaving behind the darkness of her past fruitless struggle. She was going to leave her own country finally. Deepali was presenting the delimita of the exiled people even before her time.

The waves of the South China Sea glimmered like liquid silver morning light fanned out far and wide. With his golden Noh mask on, the Sun God was slowly appearing over the misty island of Japan. For million of years the sun has been rising and going down again and rising (Haider, p. 393).

Bengal's independence could not materialize the thinking of all the female characters who were the members of Marxist movement. The lethargic struggle of Deepali for her party seems futile. After fluttering like a blind bird in the thunder of struggle brings nothing in their life. Ambiguous destination with the vague labyrinths of the path cause them to move away on the unwanted road of life. The geographical distances of the various lands and places weaved with

intricate net of life of characters is the wonderful epitome of ecology of Haier's art. Deepali on her final visit to Bengal ponders over the outcomes of all her party fellows, which are meaningless. The countless questions arising in her intuition remain unanswered. They were all exiled to different places.

What did we do? What did our generation achieve? Now it seems that we were hitchhikers who stood by the high way, raising our thumbs for a ride. A car stopped by and took some of us to Moscow others to Washington. Some of our friends got on to a camel's back and returned to Mecca. Others climbed on to a bullock-cart and went back to Banaras. The road which stopped for me broke down in the middle of the road (Haider, P. 376).

The rivers and seas surround the whole novel making this novel a marvelous ecocritical piece of literature by Haider, blended with the postcolonial perspective. The main female characters are closer to the characteristics of the vast sea in their mysteriousness. Yasmin commits suicide in drowning the river. But Deepali feels great associations with the rivers of her own homeland. The death of Yasmin in an alien river shocks Deepali. The rivers and the sea possess vital significance throughout the novel. The character's lot is associated with rivers is conspicuous. The drowning of Yasmin in an alien river is remorseful death for Deepali as this suicide could be committed in her own Bengali river.

Ecocriticism highlights the issues regarding surroundings including natural environment, physical settings and everything which is in concern to man. The literary texts which are nature-oriented, definitely depict the significance of the environment for man because the physical milieu always reflects the inner world of the characters. In postcolonial literature the natural environment occupies prominent place because it depicts the exploitation of the non-human by the human.

Through interpreting the novel on different levels it has been found that Haider's novel *Fireflies in the Mist* (1994) depicts the violence by the White man towards man and animals under the label of primitivism and barbarism. The land of Sub-continent is famous for its fertility and rich in natural wealth.

The British not only wrecked the culture pattern of the natives but also ruined the wild life and made the land barren and beguiled the natives by hiding their

true violent and cruel intentions of taking away the whole resources to their own land. The text of the novel depicts the double theory of Ecocriticism and Postcolonialism because the aeon of colonialism destroyed the environmental life of the subjugated land

The beauty of Indian Sub-continent and its partition; Pakistan, Bangladesh and India, the effects of colonialism, the suffering of the natives and the expatriates, with the natural effects of the surrounding evince the grasp of intricate style of Haider. Her enveloping the whole environment of Bengal with its pleasurable ring of landscape and the unique strands of her narration in the novel evince her art to interwind the beauty of land with colonial and postcolonial impacts on the characters. The animals, stars, moon, rivers, animals and mist all contribute to the beauty of landscape of Sub-continent which was the target of the British. The ecology of the land in the colonial tenure shows the relationship of man with nature which is inevitable because Haider weaves the story in the net of physical surrounding in the hovering situation of colonial aeon.

The association with the land and its natural beauty with its alluring charm captivate the natives to such a great extent that everything related to life seems to be related with land. That's why the colonized land remains a source of integrity for the colonizers and land is the only source which becomes utmost crucial for them.

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